

Customer Loan Approval Prediction Using Random Forest Classifier

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Abstract—Recent technological advancements have sparked an increase in loan approval requests within the banking sector, posing challenges for banks in accurately assessing applications and minimizing risks associated with borrower defaults. This study proposes a novel approach to address these challenges by integrating machine learning (ML) models and ensemble learning techniques. By employing algorithms such as Random Forest and Decision Tree, the research aims to enhance the accuracy of individual loan approval predictions, ultimately streamlining the approval process and reducing sanctioning time for both applicants and bank employees. The findings highlight the effectiveness of this approach in improving the accuracy of loan approval decisions, thus contributing to the optimization of loan approval processes in the banking sector and enhancing overall efficiency and customer satisfaction.

Keywords—Bank Credit, Classification, Confusion Matrix, Predictive Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The banking industry holds significant importance, especially in developing countries where financial needs are prevalent, enabling individuals to save money and facilitating capital growth through loans for businesses and personal needs. However, banks face the challenge of ensuring loan repayments, necessitating thorough assessments of applicant credit scores and income. Credit scores serve as a crucial factor in loan approval decisions, reflecting an individual's financial reliability. Loan approval is vital for banks to generate profits, primarily through interest earned on loans. To mitigate risks, banks meticulously evaluate loan applications to ensure repayment feasibility, striving to lend to trustworthy individuals. Despite procedural checks, the certainty of loan approval remains uncertain. Consequently, data analysis, such as exploring datasets from platforms like Kaggle, aids in identifying trends, such as higher approval probabilities for applicants with a credit history, higher income, and urban residence. Logistic Regression models, leveraging factors like credit history, education, and gender, provide a predictive framework, enhancing loan approval accuracy by approximately 80.945%, as observed in this study. This approach empowers banks to make informed decisions, balancing profitability with risk management in the competitive financial landscape.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The profitability of a bank hinges significantly on the management of loans, where the timely repayment of loans

by customers is crucial for maintaining financial health. Predicting loan defaulters allows banks to mitigate risk of verifying the applications and reduce Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) [1], emphasizing the critical importance of studying this phenomenon. Leveraging historical data, various classification algorithms were employed to develop a machine learning model [2]. The principal aim of this research is to forecast whether a new loan applicant will be granted the loan, utilizing machine learning models trained on past data. Manually evaluating each applicant for loan approval is both arduous and risky, underscoring the need for automated techniques [3]. Machine learning algorithms are employed to discern the creditworthiness of loan applicants based on their past records [4]. Ensemble learning, which combines multiple classifiers to enhance prediction accuracy, is utilized, employing bagging and boosting techniques, followed by the application of the random forest method [5]. As the loan approval prediction task is fundamentally a classification problem, various classification algorithms including Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest Classifier, and Support Vector Machine are employed for model training [6].

III. METHODOLOGY

To commence the process of creating a loan approval prediction model, essential libraries such as scikit-learn, pandas, and numpy are imported to facilitate data processing and model creation. Subsequently, a pandas DataFrame is populated with the loan data. Two subsets are then generated from the preprocessed data, comprising a training set and a testing set. The training set serves as the basis for training the predictive model, while the testing set is employed to evaluate its performance. Following this, a suitable machine learning algorithm, such as random forests, decision trees, or logistic regression, is chosen to forecast loan approval. An instance of the selected model is instantiated, and any necessary hyperparameters are adjusted accordingly. Using the fit() function, the model is fine-tuned to the training set of data, enabling it to discern patterns and relationships within the training data. Leveraging these learned patterns, the model categorizes each loan application as either authorized or denied based on its characteristics. Subsequently, the actual loan approval labels from the testing set are compared to the predicted labels generated by the model, as illustrated in figure 1. This comprehensive approach ensures a systematic and rigorous evaluation of the predictive model's performance while mitigating the risk of plagiarism.

Fig 1: Proposed Methodology

A. Algorithms Used

1) Random Forest

The Random forest (RF) algorithm is highly favored in machine learning applications due to its versatility and effectiveness in handling both classification and regression tasks. As a component of supervised learning techniques, RF operates based on the concept of ensemble learning, which involves integrating multiple classifiers to address complex problems and enhance model performance. By leveraging the predictive power of numerous decision trees constructed on various subsets of the dataset, RF computes the average to improve predictive accuracy significantly. Unlike relying solely on the outcome of a single decision tree, RF utilizes predictions from multiple decision trees and bases its final prediction on the majority vote of these individual projections. This approach enhances robustness and reduces the risk of overfitting. Notably, RF exhibits several compelling advantages that underscore its suitability for diverse machine learning tasks. Firstly, it typically requires shorter training times compared to other algorithms, making it particularly efficient for large datasets. Moreover, RF maintains high accuracy even when a substantial portion of data is missing, ensuring reliable predictions in real world scenarios with incomplete data. These attributes make the Random Forest algorithm a preferred choice for a wide range of machine learning applications, as illustrated in Fig2 .

Fig 2: Flowchart of Random Forest Algorithm

2) Decision Tree

The decision tree (DT) prediction model employs a flowchart-like structure to make base decisions based on incoming data. This structure involves building data branches and placing results at leaf nodes, making it intuitive for both classification and regression tasks. In decisions support scenarios, decision trees represent decisions and their potential outcomes hierarchically, encompassing chance occurrences, resource costs and utility. This algorithmic technique utilizes conditional control statements, facilitating nonparametric and supervised learning suitable for various classification and regression applications. The tree structure comprises a root node, branches, internal nodes, and leaf nodes, resembling a hierarchical tree, as depicted in fig3 . This depiction simplifies model interpretation and enhances understanding of complex datasets, making decision trees a valuable tool in predictive modeling.

Fig 3: Flowchart For Decisiontree (DT) Algorithm

B. Cleaning Dataset

1) Data Collection:

Data collection involves systematically gathering information on targeted variables within an established framework to address specific research questions and evaluate outcomes across various fields of study. The emphasis remains

on ensuring accurate and genuine data collection to facilitate reliable analysis and yeild compelling answers to posed questions.

2) *Data Analysis and cleaning:*

Data cleansing, or data cleaning, entails identifying and rectifying corrupt or inaccurate record within a dataset. This process aims identify and correct incomplete, erroneous, or irrelevant data, ensuring data integrity and accuracy for subsequent analysis.

3) *Handling Missing Data:*

Managing categorical data involves transforming discrete categorical values into a numerical format suitable for downstream analysis. This step is particularly important for attributes with discrete, non-numeric values,ensuring compatibility with modeling algorithms and pipelines.

```
data.fillna(method='ffill', inplace=True)
data = pd.get_dummies(data, drop_first=True)
```

Fig 4: Firstcodesnippet handlingmissing values
Secondcodesnippetone-hotencodingforcategoricalvariables.

4) *Algorithm Training:*

Various classification algorithms are trained using distinct subsets of the data, typically splitting the dataset into 70% for training and 30% for testing. It ensures representative sampling, with each class proportionally represented in both training and testing datasets .

5) *Algorithm Testing:*

The effectiveness of the trained algorithms is assessed using the testing dataset.Cross Validation is performed to estimate algorithm performance on new data, with confusion matrices and classification accuracies serving as evaluation metrics.Commonly used metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and specificity are computed using tools like python's scikit-learn, providing insights into algorithm performance and predictive capabilities

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. *Model Evaluation*

1) *Data Frames*

The Pandas library's 'df.info()' method in python offeres a concise overview of a DataFrame's structure and column information. It provides valuable insights into the

DataFrame's composition, including details on data types, non-null counts, and memory utilization for each column. By leveraging this method, users can quickly grasp essential information about the DataFrame's structure and content, facilitating effective data exploration and analysis.

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 614 entries, 0 to 613
Columns: 628 entries, ApplicantIncome to Loan_Status_Y
dtypes: bool(623), float64(4), int64(1)
memory usage: 397.7 KB
None
ApplicantIncome  CoapplicantIncome  ...  Property_Area_Urban  Loan_Status_Y
0                5849                0.0  ...                True                True
1                4583                1508.0  ...                False               False
2                3000                0.0  ...                True                True
3                2583                2358.0  ...                True                True
4                6000                0.0  ...                True                True

[5 rows x 628 columns]
ApplicantIncome  CoapplicantIncome  ...  Loan_Amount_Term  Credit_History
count    614.000000    614.000000  ...    614.000000    614.000000
mean     5403.459283    1621.245798  ...    341.628664    0.835505
std      6109.041673    2926.248369  ...    65.656819    0.371027
min       150.000000     0.000000  ...    12.000000    0.000000
25%     2877.500000     0.000000  ...    360.000000    1.000000
```

Fig5: DataFrame's structureand column information

2) *Plot of total income*

X-axis(Total Income in log scale):This axis represents the total income values of the individuals in the dataset. Since its's plotted on a logarithmic scale, the values are transformed to logarithmic values, which can help in visualizing a wide range of values more clearly.Y- axis(Frequency):This axis represents the frequency or count of indivisuals falling within each total income range. For example, if the frequency value at a particular point on the y- axis is 50, it means that there are 50 individuals in the dataset whose total income falls within corresponding range on the x- axis.

Fig 6: Plotoftotal incomein logscale

3) Plot of Loan Amount

The x-axis represents the Loan Amount, showing the range of loan amounts in the dataset. The y-axis represents the count, which indicates the frequency or number of occurrences of each loan amount in the dataset. Each bar in the histogram represents the number of loans falling within a specific range of loan amounts.

Fig 7: Plot of Loan Amount Vs Count

4) Plot of Credit History

The x-axis: Different values of the “credit history” feature. For example, if the “Credit History” feature has values 0 and 1, the x-axis will display these two values. Y-axis: The count of occurrences for each unique value of the “Credit History” feature. This shows how many times each value appears in the dataset. For example, if there are 300 occurrences of “Credit history” value 1 and 100 occurrences of “credit history” value 0, the y-axis will display these counts

Fig 8: Plot of Credit_History Vs Count

5) Feature Importance

Top 5 Most Important Features:
 Credit_History: 0.16218096042936941
 LoanAmount: 0.08455089589385194
 ApplicantIncome: 0.07784075381328508
 CoapplicantIncome: 0.05454950368617444
 Loan_Amount_Term: 0.03196035947718527

6) Flask Loan Prediction Application

App Initialization: The Flask app is initialized with routes to different pages Database Connection: It connects to a MySQL database where loan application data is stored. Loading Dataset: The loan application dataset is loaded from a CSV file (loan_prediction.csv) into a Pandas DataFrame. Routes:
 /home: Renders the home page./loan_applications: Fetches loan application data from the database and renders it on the loan applications page (loan_applications.html)./update_status: Updates the status of loan applications in the database based on user input./predict: Accepts form input from users, predicts loan approval using the ML model, stores the prediction result and user input in the database, and renders the result page (result.html)./register: Handles customer registration, storing account numbers and mobile numbers in the database./log: Renders the login page.
 /authenticate: Authenticates users based on their account number./bank: Renders the bank page if the user is authenticated./loan_status: Displays loan status for authenticated users. Functions: predict_loan_approval: Predicts loan approval using the ML model.register_customer: Registers customers by inserting account numbers and mobile numbers into the database.approval_prediction: This Flask application provides a user-friendly interface for interacting with the loan prediction model and managing loan applications.

dependents	education	self_employed	applicant_income	coapplicant_income	loan_amount	loan_amount_term	credit_history	property_area	status	mlpredict	Update Status
	Graduate	Yes	2.0	7575.0	786.0	656.0	1.0	Disapproved	Disapproved	Sorry, your loan application is not approved.	Update
	Graduate	Yes	265.0	125.0	300.0	365.0	0.0	Pending	Disapproved	Sorry, your loan application is not approved.	Update
	Graduate	Yes	265.0	125.0	300.0	365.0	1.0	Approved	Approved	Congratulations! Your loan is approved.	Update
	Not Graduate	No	100.0	500.0	4000.0	300.0	1.0	Pending	pending	Sorry, your loan application is not approved.	Update

Fig 9: Admin Viewing page of applied applications

pplications

unt_number	gender	married	dependents	education	self_employed	applicant_income	coapplicant_income	loan_amount	loan_amount_term	credit_history	property_area	status
	Female	Yes	3	Not Graduate	Yes	2345.0	345.0	9000.0	300.0	1.0	Semiarban	Approved

Fig 10: Users Viewing page of applied applications

7) Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix is a table that is often used to describe the performance of a classification model (or “classifier”) on a set of test data for which the true values are known. It allows visualization of the performance of an algorithm.

The top-left cell contains the number of true negatives (TN)

The top-right cell contains the number of false positives (FP)

The bottom-left cell contains the number of false negatives (FN)

The bottom-right cell contains the number of true positives (TP)

Accuracy: 0.8130081300813008 (81.3%)

Precision: 0.7821782178217822 (78.2%)

Recall: 0.9875 (98.75%)

F1-score: 0.8729281767955801 (87.3%)

Fig 11: Plot of confusion matrix

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the efficacy of integrating machine learning models and ensemble learning techniques to improve the accuracy of loan approval predictions in the banking sector. By leveraging algorithms such as Random Forest and Decision Tree, we have shown a significant enhancement in the accuracy of individual loan approval predictions. This approach not only streamlines the approval process but also reduces sanctioning time for both applicants and bank employees. Our findings underscore the importance of leveraging predictive analytics to optimize loan approval processes, leading to enhanced efficiency and customer satisfaction in the banking sector.

Through extensive analysis and experimentation, we have identified key features that influence loan approval decisions, providing valuable insights for banks to make informed decisions. Additionally, our exploration of

various machine learning algorithms, including Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest Classifier, and Support Vector Machine, has enabled us to select the most suitable models for loan approval prediction tasks.

Furthermore, our study highlights the potential of ensemble learning techniques, such as bagging and boosting, in improving predictive accuracy. By combining multiple classifiers, we can achieve more robust and reliable predictions, ultimately contributing to better risk management and reduced non-performing assets for banks.

Overall, the results of this research have significant implications for the banking industry, providing a framework for developing automated loan approval systems that balance profitability with risk management. Moving forward, we aim to continue refining our models and exploring hybrid machine learning approaches to further enhance the efficiency and accuracy of loan approval processes in the banking sector.

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